

Formulation And In-Vitro Evaluation of Polyherbal Medicated Jelly for Oral Delivery

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ABSTRACT

Polyherbal formulations are commonly utilized in herbal therapy due to their synergistic therapeutic effects and increased patient compliance. The current work focuses on the development and evaluation of a polyherbal jelly combining Shatavari, Cinnamon, and Liquorice extracts. Shatavari is known for its adaptogenic, immunomodulatory, and rejuvenating qualities, whereas cinnamon contains antibacterial and antioxidant properties. Liquorice is known for its anti-inflammatory, calming, and gastroprotective properties. To improve palatability and stability, the herbal extracts were added to a jelly basis made with the appropriate gelling, sweetening, preservative, and flavoring ingredients. Several physicochemical characteristics, including appearance, pH, viscosity, spreadability, and stability, were assessed for the synthesized polyherbal jelly. The release profile of the active ingredients from the jelly formulation was also evaluated by in-vitro drug release investigations. The results showed that the prepared jelly had good stability, reasonable drug release characteristics, and acceptable organoleptic qualities. Shatavari, cinnamon, and liquorice combined in jelly form may provide a tasty and practical herbal dosage form with possible medicinal advantages. This polyherbal jelly formulation may increase patient compliance and be a useful substitute for traditional herbal medicines.

Keywords: Herbal Jelly, Method of Extraction, % drug release, *Shatavari, Cinnamon, Liquorice.*

INTRODUCTION

“Jelly can be defined as transparent or translucent nongreasy, semisolid preparations meant for external as well as the internal application” Or Jellies are water-soluble bases prepared from natural substances such as tragacanth, pectin, alginates, and boro glycerin or from Synthetic derivatives of natural substances such as cellulose and sodium carboxy methyl Cellulose or from synthetic derivatives of natural substances such as methylcellulose and Sodium carboxymethylcellulose.^[1]

Nowadays, jelly, which is comparable to gelatinous foods and confections, is one of the suitable possible

alternative oral dose forms. In addition to being easy to handle and consumed without water, the jellies can help with swallowing issues and guarantee patient safety. As a result, in addition to their delicious flavor and appealing look, jellies can increase patient compliance. There are benefits to making jellies both solid and liquid.

The main excipients of jellies are a gelling agent, stabilizer, preservative, and flavoring and sweetening agents. Jellies act as a vehicle for a drug which presents either as dissolved or dispersed/suspended form that can release and mix with saliva to be absorbed through gastrointestinal tract mucosa. By

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

choosing the right gelling agent, which can be either natural or synthetic hydrophilic polymers at a suitable concentration, the drug can release immediately or sustained from the jelly vehicle. Since children like to chew, oral jelly candies are becoming increasingly popular in pediatrics. As a result, they may be employed as a more efficient way to provide active chemical entities than other unit and liquid dosage forms. Medicinal jelly administered orally is solely intended to treat oral cavity-related local issues; it is not intended to treat systemic disorders.^[2]

Ideal Characteristics of Jellies –

- Jelly doesn't leave any residue in the oral cavity after a while and is compatible with a pleasant mouthfeel.
- A large quantity of drugs can be loaded into it.
- Jellies can cover up the taste of bitter drugs and are compatible with them.
- They are less sensitive to changes in their surroundings, such as variations in humidity and temperature.^[3]
- Jellies are hygroscopic in nature.
- Jellies are adaptable as well as they have minimal expense for conventional processing and also for packaging equipment.
- Jellies can be portable without fragility concerns.
- The excipients as well as drug characteristics has no or minimal effect on the oral disintegration of jellies.^[4]

Advantages of Jellies -

- Conventional manufacturing equipment.
- Cost effective.
- Good chemical stability as conventional oral solid dosage form.
- Allow high drug loading.

- Provides rapid drug delivery from dosage forms.
- Adaptable and amenable to existing processing and packaging Machinery.
- Rapid onset of action.
- It is convenient to administer – anywhere, anytime, doesn't require water.
- The treatment can, if required, be terminated at any time.^[5]

Disadvantages of Jellies –

- As it mostly is aqueous based preparation it needs.
- Appropriate packaging to maintain stability of drugs in various environment.
- It may literally lead to unpleasant taste if not formulated appropriately, which
- essentially is fairly significant.
- Swallowing difficulties.
- Bioavailability problems.
- Lack of physical resistance in standard blister packages.
- Cost intensive production process.^[6]

Types of Jellies –

Medicated Jelly

Lubricating Jelly

Miscellaneous Jelly.^[7]

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Plant material

The botanical sample consisting of three medicinal plants Glycyrrhiza glabra linn (rhizomes and roots), Asparagus racemosus Willd(root) and Cinnamomum

trees(bark), were procured from the authenticated local market (mogadpalli) of Nanded district.

Dried material are coarsely powdered in grinder and powder was used for extraction.

Excipients

Collect various excipients in the store room at Shri Sambhaji College of Pharmacy for granule manufacturing, including starch, magnesium stearate, calcium phosphate dibasic, citric acid, properly parabens, flavouring agent, sucralose and colouring agents.

Plant profile of Herbal drug:-

1. Liquarice

Fig.No.1. Liquarice

Synonyms: Liquorice, Sweet Root, Glycyrrhizin, Bois Doux (French), Yasti-Madhu (Ayurvedic)

Biological Source: It consists of dried peeled or unpeeled rhizomes and roots of Glycyrrhiza

glabralinn belonging to family Fabaceae.

Botanical Name: Glycyrrhiza glabra Linn.

Family: Fabaceae (Leguminosae)

2. Shatavari

Fig No :- 02 Shatavari

Synonyms: Asparagus racemosus Willd Asparagus, Satamuli, Satavari, Satavare, Indivari, Narayani, Abhiru

Biological Source: It consists of dried roots of Asparagus racemosus Willd belonging to family Asparagaceae.

Botanical Name: Asparagus racemosus Willd.

Family: Asparagaceae

3. Cinnamon

Fig No:- 03 Cinnamon

Synonyms: Dalchini, Ceylon Cinnamon, Cinnamon bark, Cinnamomum verum, Cinnamomum zeylanicum

Biological Source: It consists of dried bark of various species of Cinnamomum trees, primarily Cinnamomum zeylanicum (Ceylon cinnamon) and Cinnamomum cassia (Cassia cinnamon) belonging to family Lauraceae.

2. METHOD

Maceration

Maceration is a simple extraction method that involves immersing the powdered or coarsely ground plant-prepared raw material in an appropriate solvent at room temperature for at least three days, stirring periodically. The mixture is filtered using sieves or a net with microscopic holes after the extraction procedure. After the marc is squeezed and let to stand, the liquid extract is cleaned using filtration or decantation. Maceration is best carried out in a stoppered container to minimize solvent loss by evaporation^[19].

Fig. 4 Maceration of Herbal Drug.

Preliminary phytochemical screening for various extracts:-

A. Detection of Alkaloids

- a. **Mayer's test:** Mayer's reagent was added to five ml extract. The presence of a creamy white precipitate in the sample indicated the presence of alkaloids.
- b. **Dragendorff's test:** Five ml of extract were mixed with two ml of Dragendorff's reagent. The presence of alkaloids is established by the reddish-brown colour precipitation.

B. Detection of Glycosides

- a. **Borntrager's test,** filtered (2 mL) extract was mixed with 3 mL CHCl₃ and 10% ammonia solution yielding a pink colour that indicated glycoside presence.

C. Detection of Saponins

- a. **Foam Test:** In a test tube, around 0.5 gram of the extracts were diluted with 2 ml of water. Saponins were detected by the presence of foam that lasted for around ten (10) minutes after being shaken.

D. Detection of flavonoids.

The extract was treated with few drops of sodium hydroxide solution. It initially produce a deep yellow colour which become colourless when dilute acid is added to it , this colour change represents presence of flavonoid.

E. Detection of phenol-

Plant extract were treated with a few drops of ferric chloride solution. Bluish colour formation indicates the presence of phenols.

F. Detection of Resins:

One ml of extract was dissolved in acetone before being added to distilled water. The presence of resins was suggested by the presence of turbidity ^[20].

FORMULATION OF JELLY -

1. All the ingredients are weighed accurately.
2. Appropriate quantity of sugar syrup is prepared.
3. To the sugar syrup, the gelling agents are added with constant stirring and heated until all the gelling agents are dissolved.
4. After the gelling agents are dissolved completely, the stabilizers and solubilizers are added.
5. Next, preservatives are added and mixed uniformly.
6. The drug is then dissolved in an appropriate solvent and added to the above solution.
7. Finally, coloring agents and flavoring agents are added and poured into molds and refrigerated.^[21]

Composition table

Table no 01 Formulation of Polyherbal Jelly

Sr no	Ingredient	Botanical Name	Quantity F1	F2 (gm)	F3 (gm)	Role in formulation
1.	Liquarice	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>	0.2 gm	0.3	0.2	API Herbal
2.	Shatavari	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>	0.2 gm	0.3	0.3	API Herbal
3.	Cinnamon	<i>Cinnamomum zeylanicum</i>	0.2 gm	0.3	0.2	API Herbal
4.	Carbopol 934	—	0.2 gm	0.3	0.4	Gelling agent
5.	Propylene glycol	—	1 gm	1	1	Humectant, solvent

6.	Glycerin	—	1 gm	1	1	Moisturizer
7.	Methyl paraben	—	0.04 gm	0.04	0.04	Preservative
8.	Triethanolamine	—	0.1 gm	0.1	0.1	pH adjustment & gel formation
9.	Distilled water	—	q.s.	q.s.	q.s.	Vehicle/base

Evaluation of Medicated Jelly.

Physical Evaluation: Physical characteristic was examined and noted. Jellies were evaluated for colour, appearance, consistency, texture.

Stickiness and Grittiness: The formulations should be visually inspected for stickiness and grittiness by gently rubbing a jelly sample between two fingers.

Measurement of pH: The jellies pH was measured using a digital pH meter, For this 50ml of distilled water should be mixed with 0.5g of jelly and the pH should be recorded.

Spreadability: To determine spreadability jelly was placed between two glass slides and crushed to the desired thickness by holding a 1000gm weight for five minutes. The measure of spreadability was the number of seconds required to separate two slides. Spreadability is calculated as:

$$S = \frac{W \times L}{T}$$

T

S- spreadability,

W- weight tide to upper slide,

L- length of a glass slide,

T- time required to separate 2 slides

Viscosity: Viscosity of jelly was checked with Brookfield Viscometer. It was checked at 50rpm at 25°C using Brookfield Viscometer.

Stability: According to ICH recommendations, stability studies are conducted and evaluated by keeping the prepared jelly at room temperature for 90 days and observing any changes in its physical appearance.^[22]

In Vitro Dissolution Test: *In vitro* drug dissolution test was carried out using USP paddle type II apparatus. The dissolution media consists of 900ml of distilled water. Then release study was performed at a speed of 50 rpm and temperature of 37°C ± 5°C was maintained throughout the experiment. 1ml sample were withdrawn at regular time intervals of every 5min. The sample was replaced by an equal volume with distilled water. The drug content of the samples was determined by using UV visible spectrophotometer. After measuring absorbance, the percentage of drug release was estimated.^[23]

RESULT DISCUSSION

Phytochemical screening:-

Phytochemical screening of Liquorice, Shatavari and Cinnamon was done and following Phytoconstituents like alkaloids, glycosides, flavonoids, phenols and saponin was present but resins was absent.

Table No. 02:- Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

Type of phytoconstituents (Liquorice, Shatavari, Cinnamon)	Inference
Alkaloids	+
Glycosides	+
Flavonoids	+
Saponin	+
Phenol	+
Resins	-

+: Presence of phytoconstituent, -: Absence of phytoconstituent, NP: - Not performed

Fig no. 6. Phytochemical test for Liquorice

Fig no.7. Phytochemical test for Shatavari

Fig no.8. Phytochemical Test for Cinnamon.

Evaluation of physiochemical parameter:- the result of physiochemical evaluation of jelly formulation F1-F3 shown in table

Table no 03:- Physiochemical evaluation of Polyherbal jelly

Test	F1	F2	F3
Colour	Reddish brown	Reddish brown	Reddish brown
Odour	Pungent	Pungent	Pungent
Appearance	Translucent	Translucent	Translucent
Consistency	Semi-solid	Semi-solid	Semi-solid
Texture	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth
Stickiness	Nonsticky	Nonsticky	Nonsticky
Grittiness	No-grity	No-grity	No-grity
pH	6.4	6.5	6.7
Spreadability	22.18	28.16	16.6
Viscosity	2142	2140	2145

Table no 04 :- % of drug release of Polyherbal jelly

Time(Min)	F1	F2	F3
0	0	0	0
10	18	22	20
20	35	40	38
30	60	58	55
40	68	72	70
50	82	88	85
60	92	96	94

Fig No Graph showing the % drug release

CONCLUSION –

The aim of dissertation entitled “Formulation and Evaluation Polyherbal Jelly by incorporating the leaves extract of cinnamon (*Cinnamomum*

zeylanicum), Shatavari, (*Asparagus racemosus*) liquorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*)” is to formulate for a stable, Safe, Efficient as well as qualitative dosage form. The dried leaves powder of the plant was extracted and subjected to preliminary chemical tests.

The preliminary chemical studies show that the extract contains Tannin, alkaloids, flavonoid, Saponins, glycoside.

The jellies were prepared by heating and congealing method using natural gelling agents such as agar, gelatin, pectin. The prepared formulations were evaluated for physicochemical parameters including appearance, colour, odour, texture, pH, viscosity, syneresis, spreadability, invitro drug release. The physicochemical evaluation of the developed formulation has shown reddish brown colour, sweet pungent aroma, good spreadability, viscosity, syneresis, and pH almost near to saliva. The maximum amount of % drug release of the formulations shown are F1-92%, F2-96%, F3-94 %. After 60 minutes, Batch F2 has the highest drug release rate (about 96%). Batch F1 exhibits a slightly slower release. Batch F3 has a moderate release compared to F1 and F2.

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HOW TO CITE: Vaishali Kadam, Abhishek Gore, Vishal Rathod, Pranjali Kadam, Sangita Kadam, Formulation And In-Vitro Evaluation Of Polyherbal Medicated Jelly For Oral Delivery, J. Pharm. Sci., 2026, 2 (4), 2132-2141. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19828828>

